

Title: Industrial Machine Learning is not Academic Machine Learning

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INTRODUCTION:

We present the best practices for deploying a machine learning model into production.

AIM:

Present best practices in order to facilitate the transition of your machine learning model into production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This methodology was used in 3 machine learning projects for different clients. Issues such as performance requirements, separation between the machine learning model and the implemented software, automated tests, model evolution and software evolution were considered.

RESULTS:

The methodology presented is in production, one implemented in the client's local servers and the other two implemented in a cloud environment to guarantee scalability, performance and also cost reduction with production environment. The methodology was efficient, reducing errors in production and reducing risks with evolutionary and corrective maintenance.

CONCLUSIONS:

The presented method focuses on software issues and presents a methodology that clarifies the main doubts about how to put a model of machine learning into production. The presented method has been validated in projects that are not facebook-scale. Although this is not the purpose of this study, we present some issues related to infrastructure (for example, there is a need to use cloud or if it will use Api-based models).

KEYWORDS:

Industrial Machine learning, deploying models.

BIOGRAPHY:

Tales Matos is a data Scientist at State Treasury Office of Ceará (Brazil), PHD Candidate at Federal University of Ceará and a Data Science Consultant. He has been working with data analysis for approximately 15 years, having been Business Intelligence Manager and leading

software project management at State Treasury Office of Ceará for the past 9 years. His research has focused mainly on Machine Learning, with emphasis on methods of classification and feature selection, with papers published in reputed international conferences.